

Cut out and glue the pieces, and you're ready to play!

Cards

How?

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How to detect

SCALES

Scale analysis allows the detection of stress hormones, such as cortisol, which can be more reliable, in the case of chronic stress, than the measurement in blood plasma, since it accumulates over time and thus suffers less variation.

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How to detect

WATER

In a closed aquaculture system, tank water can be analysed by biosensors to detect typical markers of stress, such as the hormone cortisol, which is released by the gills.

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How to detect

SKIN MUCUS

The skin of fish is covered by a viscous layer of mucus that serves as a first barrier of the immune system. This mucus is rich in molecular indicators that give detailed information about the animal's health status.

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How to detect

PLASMA

The blood plasma (the fluid part of the blood) transports important molecules such as ions, nutrients and, especially, proteins, which can be used as biomarkers of the animal's immune response.

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How to detect

FAECES

The analysis of the composition, consistency, and specific markers of faeces allows the digestive health and nutritional status of the fish to be assessed, and may reveal infections, parasites, or intestinal problems.

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How to detect

BLOOD

The blood is a biological fluid of transport and excretion that reflects the physiological and metabolic state of the animal. For this reason, it includes several indicators of your health status.

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How to detect

BEHAVIOUR

The behaviour of aquaculture animals is an important indicator of their stress. It is important for producers to be aware of changes such as erratic swimming patterns or loss of appetite.

Who?

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WHITE-LEGGED SHRIMP
(Litopenaeus vannamei)

- The world's leading shrimp producers are Ecuador, China, India, Vietnam and Indonesia.
- The heart of shrimp is in its head, more specifically in the cephalothorax.

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SEA BASS
(Dicentrarchus labrax)

- More than 95% of the world's sea bass production comes from aquaculture, of which 97% comes from Mediterranean countries.
- It is a gregarious species, which means sea bass live in schools of fish from the juvenile stage.

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FALSE POSITIVE

When you are asked for a card during another player's guess, you can deal a different card instead of the one that was asked for.

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ATLANTIC SALMON
(Salmo salar)

- During the first year of life, salmon are raised in freshwater land tanks, then move to offshore cages, in salt water.
- The orange colour of salmon meat is due to astaxanthin, a pigment present in the microalgae it feeds on.

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CROSS-CONTAMINATION

When a player has the "Opportunistic Parasite" card, this card is given to another player so that the second player becomes parasitized.

Effects

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RAINBOW TROUT
(Oncorhynchus mykiss)

- Trout belongs to the salmon family (salmonids), but unlike salmon, this species spends its entire life cycle in freshwater.
- Female trout can lay 3000 eggs per kilogram of body weight at one time.

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QUARANTINE

Causes a cage to be quarantined, preventing a player from entering it. The player stays at the entrance.

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ESCAPE REFLEX

This quick reflex allows you to evade effects applied directly to you.

Why?

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FISH NET

The fish net is used to manipulate animals in aquaculture. Although it is a common practice, and necessary for various routines, it stresses animals and should therefore be avoided whenever possible.

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TRANSPORTATION

In aquaculture, when animals are transported between tanks or even between companies, it is important to ensure this is done under the best conditions to minimize stress. Oxygen levels deserve particular attention.

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LOW SALINITY

Changes in the intensity of rainfall due to climate change can alter water salinity in different areas of the planet, which can cause osmotic stress in fish.

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DISEASE

The animals produced in aquaculture can contract diseases or parasites. Implementing good practices such as ensuring a healthy environment and proper nutrition can help reduce their occurrence.

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LOW OXYGEN

The warming of the Earth's atmosphere leads to a decrease in oxygen levels in the oceans, as warmer water traps fewer gases. This can severely affect aquatic animals, which depend on oxygen in the water to survive.

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POLLUTION

Heavy metals, oils, pesticides, and microplastics are pollutants often found in the sea and pose a threat to marine life, potentially causing skeletal deformities or even death of marine animals.

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INCREASE IN WATER TEMPERATURE

Climate change causes shifts in water temperature that can seriously affect fish; as they are ectothermic animals, their body temperature is impacted by the water temperature.

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HIGH DENSITY

In intensive aquaculture, the number of fish per tank/cage can be higher than that tolerated by the species. This can increase the animals' susceptibility to disease. That's why rearing densities should be optimized.

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POOR WATER QUALITY

In recirculation systems, the accumulation of compounds such as ammonium and nitrites, as well as pH changes can compromise the health of fish. These parameters should be monitored daily and corrected if necessary.

Effects

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STORM

The storm caused damage to the underwater tunnel and therefore it is closed for two rounds. Keep this card on the table with a token to mark the rounds.

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HOLE IN THE NET

One of the cages has a hole. As you must help repair it, you'll miss your next turn. Keep the card until the round you skipped has finished.

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VACCINE

The vaccine has a prophylactic effect and will therefore protect you from future diseases. Save it to get rid of the opportunistic parasite or cross-contamination.

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OPPORTUNISTIC PARASITE

Oh no, you caught a parasite! As you feel sick, you are slower. So, in the next three rounds, you only move 2 squares per round. Keep the card during these three rounds, placing a token on top to mark them.

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BOAT

You can use it to quickly move anywhere, including the laboratory for the final guess. Keep the card until you use it, or until another player uses it to make a boat crossing.

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BOOST DIET

The boost diet makes you faster, so you can choose a cage to move quickly and make a guess.

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BROKEN WALKWAY

The walkway broke and all players fell into the water. All players return to their starting place and whoever has the biosensor loses it, leaving it in the square where that player was.

AQLUA

BOAT

You can use it to quickly move anywhere, including the laboratory for the final guess. Keep the card until you use it, or until another player uses it to make a boat crossing.

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LAB KIT

This lab kit helps you detect biomarkers. So, choose a biomarker to write down to on your researcher notepad.